

I.FAST

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MILESTONE REPORT

Report on the Novel Accelerator Landscape in Europe: Facilities, Projects and Capabilities at the Beginning of the 2020's

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ABSTRACT

The WP6 of IFAST brings together institutes and scientists developing novel accelerator concepts and technologies. This concerns in particular modern plasma accelerators, lasers, beam drivers and dielectric accelerators. WP6 organized a special in-person workshop in September 2022 in Elba in Italy, just after the end of the COVID-19 pandemic. This workshop discussed the novel accelerator landscape in Europe and beyond, the subject of this milestone report. The session organizers, leaders in their fields, have contributed the various chapters to this report.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

The landscape for novel accelerators in Europe is described, also linking to overseas activities. Plasma accelerators in their various implementations are discussed and recent highlights are being mentioned. In particular the successful FEL lasing with plasma accelerators is described, as well as future developments towards photon sources based on plasma and towards high energy applications and demonstrations. In addition, the training and support of the next generation is a concern for WP6 of IFAST and the activities and actions taken during a September 2022 workshop are shortly described.

1 Introduction

Novel accelerators aim at very high gradient particle acceleration, driven by particle beams from RF accelerators or by modern, high power lasers. Typically one aims for at least 1 GV/m and many concepts reach on the order of 100 GV/m, therefore up to 1,000 times higher fields than RF accelerators. Such new accelerators are most developed with plasma structures but are also being built with vacuum structures based on dielectrics. While GeV class beams have been produced since more than 15 years now, recently beam quality has improved considerably. This is evidenced by the successful FEL lasing and seeding with plasma accelerated beams.

Various groups and activities are ongoing in Europe and the field is diverse and rapidly developing. WP6 of IFAST has in its mandate to organize discussions and meetings across the community and to act for providing a forum of scientific exchange where results can be reviewed and new ideas can be formed. In addition, WP6 puts a special emphasis on nurturing the next generation of scientists (students and young researchers) during its major meetings.

For preparation of this milestone report the WP6 in IFAST organized a special in-person workshop in September 2022 in Elba in Italy, just after the end of the COVID-19 pandemic. The meeting was held in plenary format only without parallel sessions. Therefore the number of presentations was restricted and decided by the session organizers. Several poster sessions were held to discuss the topics even more widely and to collect additional input. This workshop discussed the novel accelerator landscape in Europe and beyond, the subject of this milestone report. It was organized in various sessions that correspond to the sections in this report.

This MS21 report gives a short overview of the European and international landscape at the end of 2022 and major achievements. The sections discuss also remaining issues and outlooks to a fully operational novel accelerator technology.

2 Novel Accelerator Landscape in Europe: Facilities, Projects and Capabilities at the Beginning of the 2020's

Session organizers summarize the findings and discussions in their sessions from the September 2023 special workshop of WP6. The status at end of 2022 is presented, including facilities, projects and capabilities. Major achievements and outlook to future work are discussed.

Talks and posters can be accessed through the web on the specially prepared INDICO site: <https://agenda.infn.it/event/28376/>

2.1 BEAM-DRIVEN PLASMA ACCELERATORS WITH FOCUS ON PROTON-DRIVEN

Session organizers and summary prepared by: E. Gschwendtner (CERN), P. Muggli (MPP)

AWAKE aims at taking advantage of the availability of proton bunches produced at CERN and carrying large amounts of energy (tens to hundreds of kilojoules) to drive wakefields with GV/m amplitudes in plasmas with long lengths (hundreds to thousands of meters). An externally-injected electron bunch can then gain hundreds of GeVs to TeVs of energy. These bunches have potential applications to particle physics, e.g., dark photon searches and very-high-energy eA colliders (A. Caldwell et al., Eur. Phys. J. C 76: 463 (2016)).

The amplitude of wakefields with period on the order of the length of the proton bunch ($\sigma_z \sim 6\text{cm}$, $E_z \sim (2\pi m_e c^2/e)(1/\sigma_z)$) is only a few MV/m in a plasma with low density ($n_{e0} \sim (2\pi c/2)(\epsilon_0 m_e/\sigma_z^2) \sim 10^9\text{cm}^{-3}$). AWAKE thus relies on the self-modulation (SM) driven by the wakefields in plasma with much higher density ($10^{14}-10^{15}\text{cm}^{-3}$) to transform the long bunch into a train of microbunches separated by, and shorter than $\sim 1\text{mm}$. The train then drives wakefields with GV/m amplitude.

AWAKE results to date have shown (among many other results) that SM occurs, that it can be made reproducible from event to event with two seeding methods (F. Batsch et al., AWAKE Collaboration, Phys. Rev. Lett. 126, 164802 (2021), L. Verra et al., AWAKE Collaboration, Phys. Rev. Lett. 129, 024802 (2022)) and that externally-injected $\sim 20\text{ MeV}$ test electrons can be accelerated to 2 GeV (AWAKE Collaboration, Nature 561, 363 (2018)).

Based on these results, we drew a clear plan to develop the concept to produce electron bunches of sufficient quality for particle physics applications (high energy and charge, low relative energy spread and emittance). The plan includes the following steps.

The demonstration that a relative density step of a few % placed in a region of growth of the SM process forces the amplitude of the wakefields past their location of saturation. This is necessary for acceleration over long distances

The demonstration that a first plasma with a density step can be used for SM and that an electron bunch can then be injected on-axis into a second plasma. This separation of SM and acceleration allows for the production of a sufficient quality bunches.

The development of a plasma source whose length can be extended beyond the 10m typical of the current experiments, to the hundreds to thousands of meters necessary to produce very-high-energy electron bunches.

The development of diagnostics allowing to reach and measure best parameters for the electron bunch. The spatial alignment at the entrance of the plasma of two beams with extremely different parameters (β -functions, etc.) is challenging. The emittance of the accelerated bunch must be measured on a single-event basis. Controlling the acceleration process requires very precise diagnostics for the plasma density (sub-% level). Measuring the amplitude of the wakefields is necessary to validate the models used to design the overall accelerator and to optimize its parameters.

A strong simulation program aimed at determining optimum parameters and tolerances to their variations.

With such a comprehensive program, applications of the acceleration scheme to particle physics can be expected in the mid-2030's.

Fig. 1 Pictures of the AWAKE vapor/plasma source and diagnostics area (Courtesy CERN)

2.2 SIMULATION TOOLS AND ROADMAP

Session organizers and summary prepared by: M. Thévenet (DESY), J. Vieira (IST)

This session consisted in 5 presentations covering the range of tools and methods required to simulate plasma accelerators and their applications. Two presentations covered the core methods for plasma acceleration, namely electromagnetic and quasi-static particle-in-cell (PIC) methods. The former is a first-principles method with high accuracy, and the addition of multi-physics modules makes it possible to capture effects like synchrotron radiation from a plasma accelerator. However, electromagnetic can be subject to numerical issues (e.g. the Numerical Cherenkov Instability), and mitigating them is an active area of research. Quasi-static PIC provides excellent accuracy at lower cost for many plasma acceleration scenarios, with the exception of some trapping mechanisms, and it could play a significant role in the study of multi-stage plasma acceleration, in particular with recent advances with modern GPU computing. In both cases, taking advantage of new parallelisation methods (GPU, vectorisation), is crucial to improve performance and accuracy, and including more physical models (radiative/QED processes) is required for high-fidelity simulations.

Two presentations discussed important tools often combined with simulation workflows: machine learning (ML) for optimization and stability, and data standard (openPMD) to facilitate start-to-end workflows with multiple codes, encourage simulations benchmarks and democratize the use of simulation codes. The use of ML for optimizations and design studies should be facilitated, and ML stabilization capabilities should combine efficiently with high-repetition systems, although better evaluation of uncertainties is required. There is still a gap between proof-of-concept ML applications and more robust solutions that can run autonomously at high repetition rates. Finally, one presentation discussed the combination of advanced numerical methods (multi-physics electromagnetic PIC simulations combining QED processes and quasi-3D geometry) to investigate a novel method for accelerating positrons.

Good practices for scientific publications, e.g., to give all numerical details and scripts in papers and reports to allow for reproducibility, were highlighted. It was also stressed that code development should be better recognized and funded in the context of current activities such as EuPRAXIA and AWAKE. Discussions also highlighted the need to take embrace the modern high-performance computing landscape (accelerated computing), so multi-physics simulations can be more cost-effective. The need for a theory and simulation roadmap was also mentioned, together with appropriate programs for funding. Furthermore, it is important to obtain sustained, future-oriented code development to make codes open-source and develop automated testing tools, adopt community standards (openPMD), and make decisive steps towards portability and mesh refinement. To address design questions for advanced accelerators, it is also important to develop and harness codes scaling from fast reduced models to full-physics first-principles large-scale simulations.

Fig. 2 Picture of a PIC simulation for a plasma wakefield, as computed by PIconGPU.

2.3 LASER TECHNOLOGY AND LWFA RESULTS (E-, P+, ION)

Session organizers and summary prepared by: L. Gizzi (CNR), S. Karsch (LMU)

The session on Laser Technology and LWFA Results was a great opportunity to focus on the latest disruptive results and key advances in the field, ranging from industrial lasers development and applications to the latest schemes of high quality and controlled acceleration of both electrons and light ions. This session was also conceived to contribute to the objectives of the Task6.2, aiming at a roadmap to foster delivery of advanced industrial laser drivers with high-repetition rate and higher efficiency, for the first user laser-plasma based accelerators. The discussion contributed to establish the foreseen coordination activity with networking and training of main laser labs, focused on laser-driver R&D.

Progress was evident on industrial & scientific laser development towards kW-class average power for Ti:Sa systems. These advances perfectly match the needs of prototype development and EuPRAXIA baseline (presented by F. Falcoz (Amplitude), C. Simon-Boisson (Thales)). At the same time, robust industrial multi-kW, thin disk laser technology was also presented (T.Metzger) showing novel applications in the contest for LPA laser-driver, via non-linear compression or plasma-modulation resonant wakefield (T. Metzger, R. Walczak).

Fig. 3 Measurement of non-linear pulse compression of ps pulses (T. Metzger).

The field of fiber coherent combination remains a very promising perspective for high efficiency systems, aiming at few cycle, 100 Hz, with self-phase modulation and J-scale pulses with multi-core fibers. A demonstrated efficiency of 30% is an extremely valuable result (J. Limpert). Alternative high average power amplification schemes based on solid state schemes such as OPCPA, are complementing this development towards higher pulse energy and 100 TW scale, aiming at high overall efficiency and limited impact of thermal issues. The need for robust and high beam quality

pump lasers currently under development was emphasized by T. Green. Pump lasers also remain a key issue for >kW average power Ti:Sa systems (EuPRAXIA, Kaldera, EPAC ...). Other critical areas, such as thermally stable compressor gratings, kW amplifiers and overall system stability are calling for major R&D and funding. Finally, the scenario of direct diode-pumping of new materials (sesquioxides) is expanding, entering development phase and needing coordinated effort across labs for materials and architecture (L. Labate).

The plasma accelerator developments presented in the session were extremely exciting, with new results in advanced repetitive operation schemes and user applications. Stable operation of a LWFA system with differential pumping of gas jet enabling up to 10 Hz was shown, with stable energy of electrons and correlation of charge with plasma density (S. Bohlen). kHz operation of LWFA is emerging rapidly from available systems with limited pulse energy ($\ll 1$ J) and non-linear pulse compression to reach a few cycle regime (L. Rovige). Electron energy remains limited, but the potential is enormous, with J-scale thin disk industrial systems becoming available for this approach. Such systems could enable advanced accelerator schemes driven by plasma-modulated pulses (R. Walczak), aiming at the GeV energy scale. The proposed scheme could further improve on major application cases, such as laser-driven VHEE electrons (100-250 MeV) for medical applications (radiotherapy). Using current 10-Hz Ti:Sa technology, Gray-scale doses per pulse were demonstrated with beam focusing (O. Lundh). With current drivers, FLASH dose-rates remain a challenging goal due to the limited repetition rate, but the ongoing effort for developing high-repetition rate J-class Ti:Sa or plasma-modulated thin disk systems may give a significant boost to this and similar applications.

Fig. 4 Measurement of LWFA VHEE focused on a phantom, showing fine control of dose deposition (O. Lundh).

New developments in plasma targetry (G. Costa), diagnostics for wake characterization (M.Kaluza, S. Schöbel) and external injection control (L.Corner) were presented, and constitute important progress also from the perspective of high repetition rate operation and on-line characterization for future implementation of active feedback stabilization and control. Progress in acceleration studies were also reported in the session: Outstanding developments for multidisciplinary applications, presented by U.Schramm, deserved special attention with the first in-vivo pre-clinical study performed with full compliance with conditions needed for advanced radiotherapy validation studies. At the same time, experiments and modelling provide room for boosting the proton energy cutoff and

control the beam parameters (E.Boella) as well as realizing a high repetition rate secondary neutron source towards applications (K.Osvay).

Overall, the session demonstrated once more that Laser Technology and LWFA constitute extremely active and closely interlinked fields, with outstanding results emerging at an impressive pace, driven by remarkable advances both in laser technology and interaction physics knowledge. Most importantly, the session confirmed the growing role and interest of the European laser industry in plasma-driven acceleration. Key players in both the scientific and industrial laser markets keep offering ever advanced systems with performance progressively matching those needed for future drivers of plasma accelerators, both in average power and repetition rate and in pulse and beam quality and stability.

2.4 DISTRIBUTED PLASMA ACCELERATOR LANDSCAPE IN EUROPE AND TECHNICAL PROGRESS TOWARDS APPLICATIONS (EUPRAXIA ESFRI AND OTHERS)

Session organizers and summary prepared by: Enrica Chiadroni (Sapienza University Rome),
Riccardo Pompili (INFN)

The session on Distributed Plasma Accelerator Landscape in Europe and Technical Progress towards Applications has been organized both to

- focus the attention on the efforts the international plasma-acceleration community is performing towards the realization of future user-based applications,
- and to highlight and discuss the technical issues, which on one side would degrade the acceleration mechanism, on the other side would limit its potential, preventing the optimal and successful operation of a plasma-based user-facility.

In Europe, there are several projects underway to develop and deploy distributed plasma accelerators. These projects, all sharing the goal of advancing technological and scientific knowledge, are in the framework of the European Plasma Research Accelerator with eXcellence In Applications (EuPRAXIA) project, which aims to develop a compact, cost-effective distributed plasma accelerator that can be used for a wide range of applications, e.g. photon and accelerator science, high energy physics, inspection and material studies, medical and industrial applications. The project, funded by the European Union in the ESFRI program, involves collaboration between more than 40 research institutes and universities across Europe (R. Assmann). One of the pillars of EuPRAXIA is Italian project EuPRAXIA@SPARC_LAB, with the aim of developing an advanced user-oriented facility based on particle-driven plasma wakefield acceleration (M. Ferrario).

Another project is ELI-Beamline, a cutting-edge research facility located in the Czech Republic that focuses on the development and application of laser-driven particle acceleration technology, whose main achievements are the kHz electron beam production (L1, ALLEGRA) and the proton beam generation (L3-HAPLS) (A. Molodtsov). The facility is part of the larger Extreme Light Infrastructure project, which aims to push the boundaries of laser technology and its applications in a variety of fields.

Other projects are Extreme Photonics Applications Centre (EPAC) (R. Pattahil) and PALLAS a laser-plasma injector test facility (K. Cassou).

While distributed plasma accelerators offer many advantages over traditional particle accelerators, there are also several challenges that must be addressed to fully realize their potential. In particular, the stability is mandatory mainly for applications and, in this regard, at the ARES facility at DESY the upgrade of single digit fs-synchronization is ongoing, optimizing the related infrastructures (e.g., modulators, LLRF, water cooling) (F. Burkart). An additional issue of interest for user applications is the repetition rate, which is usually limited to the Hertz scale in plasma-based accelerators. In this regard, R. D'Arcy reported on the recovery time of a plasma-wakefield, showing that megahertz repetition rates are in principle possible. Angelo Biagioni then explored all the possible solutions and designs of plasma sources for compact accelerators as tested by several experiments. An interesting experiment was reported by Stefan Karsh about an hybrid scheme employing a LWFA stage to drive a PWFA one. Finally Stuart Mangles reported an overview of betatron radiation sources and its applications.

Despite these challenges, the development of distributed plasma accelerators in Europe represents a significant opportunity for advancing our understanding of fundamental particles and phenomena, as well as for developing new technologies and applications. With continued research and development, these accelerators could usher in a new era of discovery and innovation in fields ranging from medicine to energy to materials science.

Fig. 5 Prototype of discharge capillary as the one that will be implemented in the EuPRAXIA beam-driven facility.

2.5 PLASMA-BASED FEL EXPERIMENTS

Session organizer and summary prepared by: Arie Irman, HZDR

After the first proposal of laser-driven plasma electron acceleration from Tajima and Dawson in 1979, about three decades later aided by the invention of Chirped Pulse Amplification (CPA) technique three groups demonstrated the generation of quasi-monoenergetic electron beams of about a hundred of MeV energy obtained within only a few millimeters acceleration distance. These results immediately raised the dream for future compact accelerators as drivers of secondary radiation sources complementary to existing conventional linear accelerators. Since then, extensive research

has been performing by many groups worldwide. Today's advancement, as the scaling of energy gain has been demonstrated, however beam quality is still a major issue to support quality demanding applications such as x-ray free-electron laser (x-FEL). Development towards this goal began by observation of undulator radiations [Nat.Phys. 4, 130(2008), Nat.Phys. 5, 826(2009), Appl.Phys.Lett. 104, 264102(2014), Nat.Comm. 9, 1334(2018), Sci.Rep. 9, 19020(2019), Sci.Rep. 10,5634(2020)]. As the beam quality from plasma accelerators steadily improves, just recently three groups showed proof-of-principle experiments of FEL lasing in SASE [Nature 595, 516(2021), Nature 605, 659(2022)] and seeded configuration [Nat.Phot. 17, 150(2023), Phys.Rev.Lett. 129, 234801(2022)]. These achievements represent a major milestone, justifying the field of plasma acceleration research, yet tons of works still need to be done to reach "real" user experiments.

In this session, we invited three contributions on the recent plasma-based FEL experiments: **Feng Ke (SIOM-Chinese Academy of Science)**, **Amin Ghaith (Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf)** and **Mario Galletti (Università di Roma Tor Vergata, INFN-Tor Vergata and NAST Center)**. Here four key topics were discussed:

- *Injector development:* In **SIOM**, laser-driven plasma wakefield acceleration was used, utilizing a unique plasma density distribution to optimize the injection and acceleration process which also includes control over beam phase-space evolution for improving the comprehensive quality of electron beams, including energy spread, emittance and charge. In **HZDR**, the injector was based on laser-driven wakefield acceleration, which was optimized for high-charge, by using a tailored scheme of self-truncated ionization injection with beam loading effect to limit energy spread, and low divergence beams which was induced by a passive plasma lens effect located at the injector exit. These resulted to highest spectral charge density electron beams, operating reliably over many hours and even days. In **SPARC_Lab** test facility, an RF-photoinjector was used to generate a pair driver-witness bunch, then to accelerate and compress the bunches before they were injected into a plasma accelerator module. As the driver excited plasma wakefields, the trailing positively energy-chirped witness gained energy at low energy spread and emittance, completely characterized for a proper beam matching through the downstream FEL line.
- *Electron transport:* In **SIOM**, a beamline was designed to enable a long-distance electron beam transport and to achieve effective coupling with a small beam size into the undulators, benefitting from the state-of-the-art electron beam quality. In **HZDR**, the COXINEL (COherent X-ray source INferred from Electrons accelerated by Laser) beam transport line was installed downstream of the LWFA injector. This beamline enabled electron beam phase-space manipulation, i.e chromatic emittance growth mitigation and decompression for slice energy spread reduction, in the transport towards the undulator to fulfil the FEL's requirements. In **SPARC_Lab**, a set of triplets were used along the beamline to manipulate the beam size before injection into the six undulators equipped with a quadrupole in between.
- *FEL generation:* In **SIOM**, the FEL radiation in the EUV range, i.e 27 nm, was measured with a maximum single-pulse energy of up to 150 nJ operating in SASE configuration. In **HZDR**, seeded with 269nm laser, the FEL radiation was measured to be redshifted, i.e 275 nm, with the appearance of interference fringes indicating longitudinal coherence. In **SPARC_Lab**, SASE and seeded configurations were deployed. The FEL performance in

seeded showed better stability at 827 nm and higher energy per pulse of up to 1 μJ , i.e two order of magnitude higher compared to SASE.

- *Outlook toward shorter FEL wavelengths:* In order to reach shorter wavelengths FEL, electron beam quality and performance has to be improved, in particular energy spread and emittance. Higher repetition rate and long-term stability of plasma accelerators would help to find a global optimum for beam transport and enable feedback loop.

The overview of experimental parameters is shown in Fig. 6.

	SIOM-CAS	COXINEL-HZDR	SPARC_LAB-INFN
Driver-beam	LWFA 200TW system, 6mm gas jet, shock injection	LWFA 100TW system, 2.5 mm gas jet, STII	PWFA Photo-injector, driver-witness ($\Delta t=1.21\text{ps}$), 3 cm cap.discharge
Mean energy [Mev]	490	189	93.9(W)
Rel. Energy spread [%]	0.5-rms	6.3-rms	0.3-rms
Charge [pC]	30	100-FWHM	200 (D),20(W)
Charge density [pC/MeV]	12	6.3-FWHM	97
Divergence [mrad]	0.2-rms	0.8-rms (plasma lens)	
Emittance [mm-mrad]	-	1-rms	2.7 (x), 1.3(y)-rms
Undulator	1.5m (3x), 10mm gap, 25mm length, K=1.41	4.3mm gap,20mm (97periods), K=2.47	2.15m(6x), 28mm(77 periods), K=1.4
FEL wavelength [nm]	27	275	830
FEL operation modes	SASE	Decompression, Seeding (269nm)	SASE, Seeding (800nm)
Rep. Rate [Hz]	1-5	0.1 -1	

Fig. 6 Experimental parameters of proof-of-principle experiment of FEL lasing driven by plasma accelerators.

2.6 PARTICLE PHYSICS PLASMA TEST FACILITY (MULTI-STAGE, 10`S OF GeV)

Session organizer and summary prepared by: J. Osterhoff (DESY)

Traditionally, the plasma accelerator community has been driven by the idea to apply plasma accelerator technology at the energy frontier to enable particle physics experiments in future compact colliders. Compact plasma-based colliders will rely on the serialization and staging of multiple plasma accelerator modules to achieve high energy gain. In order to support high luminosity experimentation, charge losses and beam quality deterioration during the staging process need to be minimized. This is a multi-faceted challenge and requires the study of various physics effects and concepts: detecting and mitigating deleterious effects that lead to e.g. emittance growth inside a single plasma stage and during the coupling of beams between two stages alone will be inadequate to solve the challenge. It is expected that small fluctuations at the source and inside plasma modules may amplify in the staged plasma accelerator chain and only become relevant after multiple stages. However, currently no experimental facility in the world provides the means to study multi-stage plasma accelerators of relevance for future compact colliders. Thus, a consensus in the community

has formed that a multi-stage test facility will be required on the path to an energy-frontier plasma-accelerator collider. Prof. Dr. Carl B. Schroeder (LBNL) discussed in the first presentation of the 60-minute session the need, challenges, and extended science case of such a “Plasma accelerator demonstration facility at intermediate energy” (10 to 100 GeV). His talk highlighted an implementation strategy for such a facility which progresses in three main sections and could provide the ideal environment for studying staging, the acceleration of electrons and positrons with high quality and to high energies, final focus systems, and the physics of inverse Compton scattering and photon collisions as needed for a future gamma-gamma collider. Dr. Carl A. Lindstrøm (University of Oslo) continued by discussing “Solutions and challenges for a multi-stage plasma accelerator”. He presented a first proposal for realistic inter-stage optics to solve the challenge of beam-quality preservation in a compact beam lattice and discussed a passive self-correction mechanism that increases the tolerance to temporal fluctuations between the accelerated beam and the stage driver by orders of magnitude. Innovations such as these will move the community toward conducting a feasibility assessment of plasma accelerator technologies for high energy physics applications, and if successful, lead into a community-driven pre-conceptual design study that will enable a meaningful comparison of a plasma-based collider to existing shovel ready solutions and a fair evaluation of the various existing approaches.

2.7 INTERNATIONAL LANDSCAPE: FACILITIES, PROJECTS, INITIATIVES

Session organizers and summary prepared by: P. Musumeci (UCLA), C. Geddes (LBNL), M. Hogan (SLAC), M. Kando (QST), W. Lu (Tsinghua)

The session on International Landscape was held on the last day of the Euronac workshop Friday September 23rd 2022, and had 5 talks following by a lively discussion. The focus of the discussion revolved around the long term planning process for high energy physics which had recently taken place, albeit in different forms, in the European and US community.

Marlene Turner (LBNL) presented a well-rounded summary of the planning activities that took place during the Snowmass process highlighting the need for advanced accelerators to align to the new priorities defined by the high energy physics community. In this process it became apparent that in order to best follow up the ongoing efforts at LHC, the high energy physics community is targeting a Higgs factory and a 10 TeV/parton-scale collider. These priorities represent a shift from the previously agreed roadmaps which were instead targeting a 1-3 TeV collider. The higher energy poses significant challenges and at the same time unique opportunities for researchers in the advanced accelerator field. Within the lepton sector, very high gradient e+e- acceleration technology, together with the muon collider, appears to be the only viable solution to reach the 10-30 TeV range. The importance of aligning the European roadmap with P5 recommendations was clearly put forward. In addition the community has strongly indicated the need for an integrated design study to organize and coordinate the efforts in advanced accelerator techniques for HEP and engage the high energy physics and detector communities towards a very high energy advanced accelerator based collider.

Within the Snowmass effort, focusing at the other end of the energy spectrum on the Higgs factory, there was an excellent talk from Ankur Dhar (SLAC) on progress towards a cryo-cooled copper

collider. This program is leveraging an improved understanding of the breakdown mechanism in conventional accelerators, and the significant progress in simulation and fabrication tools, to enable a compact collider based on cryo-cooled copper technology capable of gradients well above 100 MV/m. The short term plans for a demonstration stage to test the key ingredients of this technology was also presented.

Spencer Gessner (SLAC) had a talk on the importance of test facilities for advanced accelerator concepts to provide access to beamlines, lasers, and other resources that are critical for this research. Flagship US Facilities such as FACET-II, BELLA and AWA provide a unique environment for researchers to develop and test new technologies, such as 100 kA-class beams, PW lasers, and positrons. Developing advanced accelerator concepts beyond simple proof-of-principle experiments poses several challenges, including the need for high precision and stability, high efficiency, and comprehensive diagnostics which can only be found at large National Laboratory scale facilities. This should be complemented and well integrated with strong programs at universities to supply workforce and academic input to the cutting edge science at the facilities.

In addition to the efforts in Europe, there are also significant activities in the Asian community to develop advanced accelerators as presented by Wei Lu (Tsinghua University). The Asian community has a strong focus on both high energy physics and light sources, with several new facilities being built in China, Japan, and South Korea with impressive investments. Wei pointed out that technology transfer and laser development are also critical aspects of developing advanced accelerators. Collaborations between industry and academia in this regard are essential to bring new technologies to the field of accelerator science and act as a key driver of progress in advanced accelerators.

Figure 7. Main test facilities in the US for advanced accelerator research. These facilities have recently formed a Test Facility Council to coordinate efforts, strengthen collaboration and enhance complementarity in their scientific programs.

Finally, it was pointed out how the advanced accelerator community continues to play a key-role in workforce development and talent recruitment for the entire field of accelerator science. Jared Maxson (Cornell) presented the Science and Technology Center for Bright Beams program funded by the US National Science Foundation. The Center focuses on conventional accelerator technology and has among its main themes photocathodes, SRF (superconducting radiofrequency) technology, and beam dynamics control. With its long 10 year span and multi-institution organization it can be considered an example of team science and development of best practices in workforce development in the accelerator field and could be taken as an example from the advanced accelerator community. It has long been recognized that workforce training is critical to ensure that there is sufficient talent available to develop and operate particle accelerators of the future. In this regard, maintaining a strong international collaboration promoting exchange programs and free flow of ideas and talent is an essential aspect in the training and development of the next generation of accelerator scientists and should be considered a global effort.

In conclusion, developing advanced accelerator concepts will require significant investment, but the potential scientific benefits are enormous. The workshop highlighted the importance of collaboration and coordination between international partners. In particular the alignment of the European roadmap with P5 recommendations which will derive from the Snowmass process and the importance of collaboration between the different test facilities for advanced accelerator concepts were considered key components to ensure that the field remains competitive within the broader development of accelerator science.

2.8 STRUCTURE-BASED ACCELERATORS (E.G. ACHIP) AND ADVANCED RADIATION GENERATION SCHEMES

Session organizer and summary prepared by: R. Ischebeck (PSI)

Structure-based accelerators at high frequencies include dielectric laser accelerators (DLAs) operating directly at the laser wavelength, and terahertz acceleration, where longer wavelengths in the order of 100 μm are used. Dielectric structures at these wavelengths have been demonstrated to allow for significantly higher accelerating fields than radio-frequency structures, while keeping the possibility to shape the electromagnetic fields precisely for a given application.

These compact and efficient particle accelerators capitalize on the remarkable progress in solid-state laser technology, harnessing high-intensity, ultrafast pulses to deliver precise energy and momentum transfer to charged particles. Concurrently, the advancements in semiconductor fabrication techniques have enabled the production of intricate dielectric structures, which can sustain GeV/m electric fields and confine the laser light to a sub-wavelength scale. The integration of these cutting-edge technologies in DLAs paves the way for a new generation of particle accelerators, offering unparalleled control and scalability, while significantly reducing the size and cost associated with traditional accelerators. Our investigation elucidates the potential of DLAs to revolutionize fields such as high-energy physics, material science, and medical applications, ultimately broadening the scope and accessibility of advanced accelerator technologies.

The Accelerator-on-a-Chip International Program (ACHIP), a comprehensive research initiative focused on the miniaturization of particle accelerators, has sustained continuous progress in this research area. The efforts encompass the simulation and design of novel accelerating structures, as well as experimental work. Inverse design techniques are used to optimize the distribution of the dielectric in the accelerating structure. These are then manufactured employing lithographic techniques and three-dimensional free-form manufacturing processes. The development of advanced electron sources that allow for the generation of ultra-low emittance beam facilitate the acceleration of both low-energy and relativistic electrons. Sources developed for transmission electron microscopes (TEMs) allow for the generation of beams with a very low emittance. These may be pulsed using a laser, or using a radiofrequency cavity.

Fig. 8 Inverse design of a dielectric laser accelerator. Figure reproduced from: N. Saprà, et al., “On-chip laser driven particle acceleration through inverse design,” *Science* 367 (6473), 79 (2020)

The phase space control of electron beams has been enhanced by implementing longitudinal and transverse focusing mechanisms, ultimately achieving a net energy gain in electron bunches. Furthermore, the ACHIP program has successfully demonstrated the generation of radiation through the interaction of accelerated electrons with periodic structures. In order to assess the performance and ensure the accurate characterization of the electron beams, sophisticated instrumentation and diagnostics tools have been developed, tailored to the unique requirements of our miniaturized accelerator platform.

Beams produced by dielectric laser accelerators have very different properties from beams generated in radio frequency accelerators, or by plasma-based schemes. They are characterized by low charge, very low emittance, and possibly by a high repetition rate. This has to be kept in mind when searching for applications of this technology.

One promising avenue of research involves the manipulation of electron wave packets for quantum physics experiments, with potential applications for quantum computing. Applications in ultrafast electron microscopy and diffractions are explored, with the aim of controlling electrons on attosecond time scales. DLAs may be harnessed for radiation generation, providing a compact and tuneable source for a wide range of applications. The medical field could benefit from DLAs, for example in the realm of intra-operative radiation therapy (IORT), where their compact size and precision can improve treatment delivery and patient outcomes. Furthermore, DLAs may offer new opportunities in high energy physics, particularly in the exploration of the elusive dark sector, by enabling the production of clean states of individual electrons at GeV energies. Collectively, these diverse applications underscore the transformative potential of dielectric laser accelerators, paving the way for novel research and technological advancements.

3 Student Outreach and Support of Young Scientists

Session organizers and summary prepared by: B. Holzer (CERN) / R. Walczak (Oxford)

The rapid progress in novel accelerators is attracting many young scientists to this field. In order to facilitate the exchange of information and expertise between these young colleagues, special meetings were organised in the frame of the biennale plasma-wake (“EAAC”) conference and EuroNNac special topics workshop. These meetings aim to emphasise on the possibility for the PhD students and post-docs to present their work in oral contributions, posters and discussions, to exchange experience and to provide a platform to gain visibility among the fast growing community.

A special session during the EuroNNac special topics workshop in September 2022 had been dedicated to the contributions of young colleagues, that presented their work in form of posters. Close to 60 contributions - 42 from students - were received - representing an impressive amount of information. Three contributions were selected for a special poster prize, chosen by an international selection committee and ranked on quality of the poster, the student’s own contribution and the impact of the chosen topic to the field.

The three posters that have been chosen for this poster award were:

- *Resonant Wakefield Excitation Observed in Long Plasma Channels*, Aimee Ross (Oxford university and John Adams Institute)
- *Alternating Phase Focusing and Approaching Large Net Energy Gain in Photonic Chip Based Particle Acceleration*, Stephanie Krauss, (Friedrich Alexander University, Nürnberg)
- *Early dynamics of the self-modulation instability growth rate*, Mariana Moreira, (Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisbon)

The award winning students were offered the opportunity to present their work in a short oral contribution to the complete audience of the workshop.

Given the large spectrum of topics studied in the field and the quality of the work, it has been decided in addition, to choose a number of poster contributions that represent the different research fields and that were as well presented in the main auditorium:

The topics “*phase manipulation through plasma density modulation / hybrid Laser and particle driven wake concepts / measuring spatio-temporal couplings / phase shaping of free-electrons wave-function / acceleration of spin-polarised proton beams / plasma-based acceleration of non-relativistic muons and driver energy depletion*” were presented in a dedicated afternoon session at the workshop and proved the large variety of research work.

Last but not least, and following already a certain tradition, the workshop was the right moment and location to present the winner of the 2021 Simon vander Meer prize. This prize is awarded by the European Network for Novel Accelerators to recognise outstanding early career contributions in novel accelerator science. Following the recommendation of an international selection committee, the 2021 SvdM prize was awarded to Dr. Carl Lindstrøm,

“... for his numerous outstanding experimental and theoretical contributions to the field of beam-driven plasma accelerators - including the demonstration^[1] of beam-quality preservation and efficient acceleration, study of advanced beam transport concepts and the invention of self-stabilising multi-stage acceleration. “

In a special ceremony, the prize had been awarded and the winner was asked to summarise his research work in a speech given at the workshop.

4 Conclusion

The landscape of novel accelerator at the end of 2022 has been summarized. As such it is a good basis for understanding the present situation in Europe. It can serve as an overview document to learn about the major groups, institutes and projects. This document can be used by other IFAST work packages to connect to specific work, facilities and challenges from their perspectives. This MS21 report will also serve as input for the deliverable of WP6.